

Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of some new pyrazolothiadiazoles and their azetidinones

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Several 2-arylideneamino-5-(*N*¹-pyrazolomethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4) and 1-[5'-(*N*¹-pyrazolomethyl)-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]-4-substituted-3-chloro-2-azetidinones (5) have been synthesised and tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Pyrazoles, 1,3,4-thiadiazoles and 2-azetidinones possess various biological activities¹. The 2-azetidinones ring in pyrazole have been inserted by annulation of chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine in dioxane.

Results and Discussion

Ethyl chloroacetate with pyrazole yielded ethyl *N*¹-pyrazoloacetate (1), which on reaction with thiosemicarbazide resulted *N*¹-pyrazoloacetylthiosemicarbazide (2). Compound 2 on dehydrative annulation by conc. H₂SO₄ afforded the thiadiazole (3), which on condensation with various carbonyl compounds furnished 2-arylideneamino-5-(*N*¹-pyrazolomethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4a-j). The β-lactam moiety was introduced in compounds 4 by cycloaddition of chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine in dioxane to yield 1-[5'-(*N*¹-pyrazolomethyl)-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]-4-substituted-3-chloro-2-azetidinones (5a-j) (Scheme 1). Purity of the compounds was monitored by TLC.

Compounds 4 and 5 were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Shigella dysenteriae* (*Sd*), *Shigella flexneri* (*Sf*) and *Streptococcus aureus* (*Sa*) at 50 and 100 ppm concentrations using streptomycin as control. Antifungal activity was performed against *Cryosporium pannical* (*Cp*), *Aspergillus niger* (*An*) and *Rizophus oryzae* (*Ro*) by filter paper disc method² at 100 and 500 ppm concentrations using griseofulvin as control. The following compounds were found active against the noted bacteria : **4b** (*Sd*, *Sa*), **4c** (*Sd*, *Sf*, *Sa*), **4d** (*Sd*, *Sa*), **4i** (*Sf*, *Sa*), **5b** (*Sd*, *Sf*), **5d** (*Sd*, *Sf*, *Sa*), **5g** (*Sd*, *Sa*), **5h** (*Sd*, *Sf*). The following compounds were found active against the noted fungi : **4b** (*Cp*, *An*, *Ro*), **4c** (*Cp*, *An*), **4e** (*An*, *Ro*), **4f** (*Cp*, *An*), **4i** (*Cp*, *Ro*), **5b** (*Cp*, *An*), **5c** (*Cp*, *An*, *Ro*), **5d** (*Cp*, *An*, *Ro*), **5g** (*Cp*, *Ro*), **5h** (*Cp*, *Ro*).

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker DRX (200 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal standard. The compounds gave the satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

*Ethyl N*¹-pyrazoloacetate (1) : A mixture of pyrazole (0.3 mol), ethyl chloroacetate (0.3 mol) and anhyd. K₂CO₃ (5.0 g) in dry acetone (70 ml) was refluxed for ~16 h on a water-bath. Acetone was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised

	R ₁	R ₂		R ₁	R ₂
4,5b	H	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	g	H	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄
c	H	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	h	H	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄
d	H	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	i	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅
e	H	C ₄ H ₃ O	j	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅
f	H	CH=CHC ₆ H ₅			

Scheme 1. Reagents (i) ClCH₂COOC₂H₅, (ii) H₂NNHCSNH₂, (iii) H₂SO₄/liq. NH₃, (iv) R₁COR₂, (v) ClCH₂COCl/(C₂H₅)₃N

from ethanol as light yellow crystals (68%), m.p. 142–143°; ν_{max} 2980 (CH₂), 1720 (C=O, ester), 1500 (pyrazole ring), 1456 cm⁻¹ (N-CH₂); δ 1.20 (2H, t, ↓ 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 3.61 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.10 (2H, q, J, 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃) and 6.41–6.60 (3H, m, pyrazole-H).

Note

*N*¹-Pyrazoloacetyl-thiosemicarbazide (**2**) : A mixture of the pyrazole ester (**1**; 0.09 mol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.09 mol) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~8 h. It was then cooled, concentrated and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform as light green crystals (70%), m.p. 196–197°; ν_{\max} 3330 (NH-NH₂), 3033 (C-H), 1510 (pyrazole ring), 1670 (CONH₂), 1461 (N-CH₂) and 1135 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 3.60 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 6.55–6.85 (3H, m, pyrazole-H) and 8.28 (4H, m, NHHCSNH₂).

2-Amino-5-(*N*¹-pyrazolomethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**3**) : A mixture of **2** (0.05 mol) and conc. H₂SO₄ (15 ml) was kept overnight at room temperature, then poured in ice-cold water, neutralised with liq. ammonia and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture as light yellow crystals (75%), m.p. 176–178°; ν_{\max} 3355 (NH₂), 1500 (pyrazole ring), 1600 (C=N) and 710 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ 3.61 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.25 (2H, s, NH₂) and 6.55–6.90 (3H, m, pyrazole-H).

2-Benzylidenylamino-5-(*N*¹-pyrazolomethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**4a**) : A mixture of **3** (0.018 mol), benzaldehyde (0.018 mol) and glacial acetic acid (0.018 mol) in methanol was refluxed on a water-bath for ~5 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform-benzene mixture as brown crystals (80%), m.p. 155–156°; ν_{\max} 1500 (pyrazole ring), 1580 (N=CH), 1615 (N=C), 1460 (N-CH₂) and 695 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ 3.70 (2H, s, NCH₂), 4.90 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.90–7.90 (8H, m, pyrazole and ArH). Similarly, other compounds (**4b-j**) were synthesised.

1-[5'-(*N*¹-Pyrazolomethyl)-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]-4-phenyl-3-chloro-2-azetidinone (**5a**) : To **4a** (0.014 mol), triethylamine (0.014 mol) in dioxane (40 ml) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.014 mol) were added dropwise at room temperature and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture as grey crystals (65%), m.p. 164–165°; ν_{\max} 1755 (C=O), 1500 (pyrazole ring), 1615 (C=N), 1460 (N-CH₂) and 692 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ 3.71 (2H, s, NCH₂), 4.10 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, N-CH), 5.00 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, CHCl), 7.00–7.82 (8H, m, pyrazole and ArH). Similarly, other compounds (**5b-j**) were prepared.

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